

Catalytic Hydrogen Waves at Dropping Mercury Electrode (with Special Reference to Thio Compounds), 1970-1996

K. SARASWATHI*, K. YAMUNA and P. PRAMEELA

Department of Chemistry, S. V. University, Tirupati-517 502

Manuscript received 12 January 1993, revised 16 June 1997, accepted 25 June 1997

A review on the use of catalytic hydrogen waves of thio compounds for the detection of low concentration of metal ions present in different environmental samples and limitations of the method are discussed.

The present communication evaluates the effectiveness of electrochemical methods for trace analysis because of their low cost, high sensitivity and easy facilities for measurement. Electrochemical methods represented by advanced modes of voltammetry such as d.c. polarography, a.c. polarography, cyclic voltammetry, oscillopolarography and differential pulse polarography have gained prominent position in recent years for trace analysis. The use of catalytic hydrogen waves enhances the sensitivity of polarographic analysis compared to ordinary diffusion-controlled waves. These waves have been applied to trace analysis of high purity materials, ores, various contaminants in air, water, food, sewage-sludge etc., with satisfactory results due to their high sensitivities.

Keeping in view the interest of various research workers and the importance of catalytic hydrogen waves at DME in polarography, this article reviews the work done on thio compounds in this field during the period 1970-1996. An emphasis has been placed on references that have appeared in analytical and chemical abstracts and those which have been published in reputed journals. Here we summarize the experimental conditions and the applications of some of the important catalytic hydrogen waves at mercury electrode.

Brief note on catalytic currents

Polarographic currents controlled by a rate of reaction occurring at the surface of the electrode and in the vicinity of the electrode in addition to diffusion are called catalytic currents^{1,2}. In the first type, the limiting current of an electroactive substance is increased in the presence of a catalyst which itself is either polarographically inactive or reduced at considerably more negative potentials. The mechanism for appearance of a catalytic wave is

where Z is not reducible at a certain potential if present alone, but causes the current obtained from the reduction of an electroactive substance O at that potential to increase by reacting with the product R to regenerate O. Examples of this type are the reduction of Fe^{III}, Mo^{VI}, Ti^{IV}, V^V in the

presence of different oxidizing agents, such as hydrogen peroxide, chlorate, perchlorate, nitrate, hydroxylamine etc., which act as catalysts.

The second type of catalytic currents mostly seen with metal complexes are catalytic hydrogen waves. They are observed at less negative potentials than the usual waves of hydrogen discharge in the presence of metal complexes. Thus the catalysts diminish the hydrogen overvoltage, accelerating the hydrogen ion discharge. The process occurs in solutions containing a base B that is not reducible but can catalyze the reduction of protons,

HA is a hydronium ion or another proton donor. As a result of electron transfer (ii) to the protonated form of the catalyst an unstable uncharged particle is formed. The HB particles enter into a bimolecular interaction (iii) regenerating the catalyst base and liberating molecular hydrogen. The catalyst B is again protonated by step (i), discharged by step (ii) and regenerated by step (iii). These catalytic waves are obtained with many organic ligands, which include amines, amino acids, proteins, thiols, disulfides, alkaloids and phosphines.

Very few references are available in the literature on review articles of catalytic polarographic currents. Further, these articles concentrated mainly on the development of the process, theory of catalytic currents and their use in analytical chemistry³⁻⁶. The theory of catalytic currents was also explained by Chizuko and Hiroaki⁷ giving simple algebraic expressions. Sheau-shya⁸⁻¹⁰ gave an account on polarographic catalytic waves and its analytical uses in

China. The catalytic polarographic currents of complexes of platinum group of metals and their applications in trace analysis was reviewed by Ezerskaya and Kiseleva¹¹. Recently, Kheifets and Zaitsev¹² published an article on the uses of catalytic polarographic currents for detection of low concentrations of chemical substances present in natural waters.

Organic thio compounds are important in view of their wide applications in organic and inorganic analysis, biochemistry, pharmaceutical chemistry, environmental chemistry and also mimicking the properties of biological compounds, such as cysteine, proteins, bovine serum albumin etc. These compounds are found to give catalytic hydrogen waves in presence of Co^{II}, Co^{III} and Ni^{II}. There is no review specially on catalytic hydrogen waves obtained with such important compounds as thio compounds. Hence, the present article reviews the work on catalytic hydrogen currents due to organic thio compounds in the presence of transition metal ions and their use in the detection and determination of traces of these metal ions in various unknown samples.

Catalytic hydrogen waves due to thio compounds

Catalytic hydrogen currents of low molecular weight thiols as cysteine, cysteine ethyl ester, cysteamine, thioglycolic acid, thiosalicylic acid in buffers, such as borax, boric acid, tris-hydrochloric acid, phenol-sodium phenolate, ammonium chloride-ammonium hydroxide etc. in the presence of cobalt(II) ions exhibit typical kinetic characteristics and the rate-determining step is a chemical process^{13,14}.

Proteins containing -SH or -SS- groups in an ammoniacal buffer in presence of Co^{II} or Co^{III} salts exhibit catalytic waves which are used to characterise the proteoharmones by mixing them in various proportions¹⁵. The nature of the polarographic protein (containing S atoms) waves in ammonia buffer containing hexamine cobalt chloride was studied in detail by Kuznetsov¹⁶. Senda *et al.*¹⁷⁻¹⁹ reported a theoretical equation for the Brdicka current produced by the protein in an ammoniacal buffer containing cobalt salt, and explained the properties of the protein-cobalt(0) complex which catalyses the hydrogen evolution. They also showed that the catalytic activity of the protein-zero valence cobalt complex increases with the increase in temperature.

The catalytic hydrogen waves of thiamine were used for its determination in ammoniacal media in the presence of cobalt(II) or cobalt(III) by Lopez-Fonsica²⁰. A new catalytic current other than Brdicka current was reported by Anzerbacher and Kalous²¹ for cysteine in cobalt(II) solution in an ammoniacal buffer on an HMDE. This result was attributed to the pre-electrolysis of Co^{II} which is deposited on the electrode. This deposited cobalt was found to be different in nature in the presence of cysteine due to existence of various Co^{II} complexes in the solution which were reduced at different potentials.

The effect of thiourea and its alkyl derivatives on the reduction of various cations as Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} was studied in neutral medium by classical and pulse polarography by Vanlaethiem-Meuree²², who indicated that these sulfur compounds give catalytic hydrogen currents similar to those by proteins. A similar catalytic hydrogen wave of cysteine and thioglycolic acid in ammoniacal solution containing cobalt(II) salt was reported by Babkin *et al.*²³. Kadlecek *et al.*²⁴ showed that the catalytic activity of structurally similar thiols decreased with decreasing values of the stability constants of the complexes with Co^{II} ions. The catalytic hydrogen waves caused by mercapto derivatives formed in a reduction process of organic sulfoxides and sulfides at DME in aqueous ethanol was indicated by Johansson and Wendsjo²⁵. They explained the behavior of catalytic waves as a function of the adsorptivity of the catalysts and their polarisation in the high electric field of the double-layer. They also mentioned that in the case of sulfoxides all the products acted as catalysts and gave two catalytic waves corresponding to pyridine and mercapto derivatives whereas sulfide derivatives gave only one catalytic wave corresponding to the product, 2-methylpyridine²⁵.

Kolthoff *et al.*²⁶ studied the catalytic hydrogen currents observed with native and treated bovine serum albumin (BSA) in various buffers, such as ammonia, borate and tris-buffer. They clearly indicated that both nitrogenous and sulfhydryl groups of BSA and treated BSA were responsible for the appearance of catalytic hydrogen waves which were also referred to as pre-sodium waves. Catalytic hydrogen currents due to the presence of heme and -SH groups in horse myoglobins, sperm whale, bovine and human haemoglobins in buffer solutions containing cobalt salts at DME and HMDE were reported by Kinoshita *et al.*²⁷. A direct correlation between the number of -SH group content of bovine or human haemoglobin and the catalytic hydrogen currents was established by Kuik *et al.*²⁸. A similar correlation between the number of -SH groups and the catalytic current was shown by Kuik and Krassowski²⁹ using solutions containing bovine, ovine, dog, human, rabbit, pigeon haemoglobins and bovine or human methaemoglobins in several ammonia and cobalt chloride concentrations where linear correlation between the current and the number of -SH groups in the molecules was shown.

The catalytic hydrogen wave of ethyl thioglycollate in ammoniacal cobaltous chloride solution was presumed to be due to complex of cobalt thioglycollate by Saxena and Chaturvedi³⁰. The polarogram of cobalt in ammonia buffer in the presence of thiols at HMDE after pre-electrolysis, as recorded by Kadlecek *et al.*³¹, clearly indicated a catalytic hydrogen wave which was attributed to a deposit of cobalt(0) on mercury, which lowered the overvoltage of hydrogen and gave the catalytic hydrogen wave. The catalytic activity of three cysteine-containing dipeptides in

ammoniacal medium in the presence of cobalt chloride was investigated by Kadlecěk and Kalous³². The behavior of cobalt(II) at DME in a borax buffer in presence of a number of pyrimidine thiols was examined by Lopez *et al.*³³. The results indicated that the 1 : 1 complex was responsible for the catalytic prewave through adsorption on mercury of the reduction product of the complex. Galvez *et al.*³⁴ suggested a mechanism for production of catalytic hydrogen wave obtained with dimethyl dithiocarbamate in the presence of cobalt(II) in ammonia buffer. According to them, the reduction product of Co^{II} complex of thio compound, Co(0) adsorbed over mercury was responsible for the catalytic hydrogen wave. Ruiz and Moreno³⁵ observed two catalytic hydrogen currents in the reduction of 2,2-dithiobenzoic acid in the presence of cobalt(II) at DME. The first wave was assumed to result from protonation of adsorbed cobalt(0)-ligand complex while the second wave was attributed to the lowering of hydrogen overvoltage by the adsorbed metallic cobalt on the mercury. The first wave was utilized for the determination of the thio compound and in the amperometric titration of cobalt(II) with EDTA. Zhao and Wang³⁶ designed a method for the determination of cobalt in various samples upto 1×10^{-10} M by catalytic polarography in phenanthroline-thiourea-ethanol amine system. A novel method based on the accumulation of cobalt complex, [Co SCN NO]⁺ on HMDE was described by Gao *et al.*³⁷ down to 0.3 nM concentration of the metal using differential pulse voltammetry.

Polarographic catalytic hydrogen waves of thio compounds are observed not only with Co^{II} or Co^{III} but also with a few other transition metal ions. Bis(hydroxymethyl)-dithiocarbamate and dimethyl dithiocarbamate in acetate buffer in the presence of Mn^{II} and Fe^{II} in aqueous ethanol and aqueous DMF media were found to give catalytic hydrogen waves by Budnikov *et al.*³⁸. These waves were used in the determination of traces of the fungicide Ferbam in the range of 0.5 to 5×10^{-3} $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. Co^{III} and Fe^{III} with thiosemicarbazones of pyruvic acid and benzoyl formic acid gave catalytic hydrogen waves, as described by Toropova *et al.*³⁹. Budnikov *et al.*⁴⁰ obtained catalytic hydrogen currents at DME in solutions of nickel and cobalt complexes with (carboxymethyl) and (carboxyethyl)-dithiocarbamates in KCl medium. The current was rectilinearly related to Co concentration in the range of 5 to 40 μM . The catalytic hydrogen waves of Co and Ni complexes with alkyl xanthates of the general formula M(ROOCS₂) (where R = Me, Et, Pr, iso-Pr, Bu and n-Pentyl) and dialkyl dithiophosphates of the type M[(RO)₂PS₂]X (where R is Et and iso-Bu) were studied at DME in DMF and EtOH-H₂O solutions using Et₄NClO₄ as supporting electrolyte⁴¹. The complexes of Fe^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with bis(2-hydroxyethyl)-dithiocarbamate in H₂O-EtOH medium in acetate buffer produced catalytic hydrogen waves whose currents were proportional to the concentration of metal ions in the range of 5 to 0.5 μM ⁴². The catalytic hydrogen currents of Fe^{III}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with ethyl xanthate in acetate buffer was

reported by Frolova *et al.*⁴³ by extraction voltammetry. The method was applied to waste-water analysis.

The catalytic wave of Ni^{II}-cystein system in ammonia buffer revealed three peaks in the potential range where catalytic reduction of hydrogen occurred. According to Kuik^{44,45}, the shape and height of these peaks depended on the molar ratio of Ni and cysteine, the composition of the buffer, temperature etc. The catalytic hydrogen waves produced by nickel in cysteine containing acetate buffer was examined by Banica and Calusaru^{46,47}. The method was compared spectrophotometrically and found that Ni^{II}-complexes with cysteine were involved in electrode reactions which acted as catalysts for hydrogen evolution. The same was identified using isotropically different solutions and was explained in the form of two possible reactions. The first was considered as protonation of the amino group of cysteine and the second as the reaction with Ni^{II} to give a reducible complex which acted as a catalyst. Nickel(II) was also found to give two catalytic hydrogen waves in the form of humps by nickel-mercaptobenzoxazole system⁴⁸. A reaction scheme for catalytic hydrogen prewave due to nickel-glutathione at pH 7.0 was suggested by Elena *et al.*⁴⁹.

Simultaneous determination of copper, nickel, cobalt and cadmium in human hair and tea samples without interference with each other using catalytic hydrogen waves due to 1-(2-quinolyazo)-2,7-dihydroxynaphthalene complexes was reported by Zhengaqi *et al.*⁵⁰. The polarographic wave of Cu^{II} in the presence of H₂SO₄ and thiourea was reported by Biernat and Syzmaszek⁵¹ who showed that the wave was due to the catalytic reduction of hydrogen ions at low overvoltage. An indirect polarographic method for the determination of Cu^{II} based on the highly stable complex, Cu^{II}-salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone was developed by Revathi and Palaniappan⁵². The method was applied for the micro-determination of copper in high purity reagents upto 0.5 ppm. The polarogram of Cu^{II} in HCl-thioglycollic acid-1,10-phenanthroline exhibited an adsorptive catalytic wave which was applied for trace amounts of Cu in waste and natural waters; the limit of detection was 0.03 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ ⁵³.

The heterocyclic azo complexes of copper on accumulation on static mercury drop electrode provided the basis for the direct cathodic stripping voltammetric analysis⁵⁴. The polarographic determination of indium with thioglycollic acid and 2,2'-bipyridyl in acetate buffer was proposed by Du *et al.*⁵⁵. The limit of determination was 5 ng ml⁻¹ and was used for the determination of trace quantity of indium in waste waters. Simultaneous determination of traces of cadmium and indium was performed by Du and Huang⁵⁶ using acetate buffer in the presence of thioglycollic acid-2,2'-bipyridyldiphenylguanidine. The detection limits were 3×10^{-9} and 1.2×10^{-9} mol dm⁻³ for Cd and In respectively and the method was applied to industrial waste water analysis.

Medyantseva *et al.*⁵⁷ observed catalytic hydrogen waves of ruthenium and rhodium in acidic media in presence of diethyl dithiocarbamate in dimethylformamide. The method was applied to the analysis of Cu-Ni sulfide ore and the limit of detection was 20 nM for Rh and 8 nM for Ru. The rhodium-thiosemicarbazide complexes were studied by ir and uv spectroscopy and polarography. The 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complexes catalysed the reduction of hydrogen ions at DME and gave catalytic hydrogen waves which was used for quantitative determination of rhodium⁵⁸. The factors that affected the catalytic hydrogen currents arising during the reaction of rhodium with thiosemicarbazide were studied and optimum conditions for the determination of Rh was developed by Ezerskaya *et al.*⁵⁹. The catalytic hydrogen currents due to complexes of rhodium with organic thio compounds were studied to improve the sensitivity of the method for the determination of rhodium⁶⁰. The polarogram of rhodium-DL-2,3,5,6-tetrahydro-6-phenylimidazothiazole chloride showed the formation of 1 : 1 complex which was adsorbed on the mercury electrode and catalysed the proton discharge responsible for the catalytic hydrogen wave⁶¹. A stable complex of rhodium with dichloropyridylazodimethylaminoaniline in acetate buffer at pH 5.0 was used by Zhang Zhanyi *et al.*⁶² for the determination of rhodium in parts per trillion level. The polarogram of palladium at pH 1.5 in the presence of thiosemicarbazide indicated the presence of catalytic hydrogen wave whose current was proportional to palladium concentration in the range 0.5–11.0 ppm of the metal⁶³. A catalytic polarographic method was reported by Dan and Re⁶⁴ for trace amounts of tungsten in the concentration range 0.004–1.4 µg ml⁻¹ in acidic medium using mercaptobenzothiazole complex.

From the above literature survey, it is clear that the catalytic hydrogen currents obtained with transition metal ions in the presence of organic thio compounds are mostly used for trace level analysis which is otherwise not possible with ordinary diffusion-controlled waves. The detailed mechanism for these catalytic currents is not fully understood so far. A few workers have suggested a brief mechanism and the important factors involved in these reactions. The mechanisms of Mader and his associates¹⁴ for Co^{II}-thiol complexes are found to be satisfactory as they incorporate almost all mechanisms reported earlier and also follow the general reactions suggested for catalytic hydrogen waves. According to them catalytic hydrogen currents are of two types, namely, Brdicka currents having one maximum and non-Brdicka catalytic hydrogen currents with two maxima. It is seen that low molecular weight thiols under certain experimental conditions give Brdicka currents whereas mercaptoaniline and related aromatic compounds give non-Brdicka currents and are identified with notations A and B at a positive potentials of limiting current plateau of metal ion. Both Brdicka and non-Brdicka catalytic hydrogen waves can be observed with all thiols under suitable experimental conditions. In

both the cases, the rate-determining chemical reaction is the protonation of the catalytically active species. Based on various effects such as pH, temperature, ionic strength etc, mechanisms are suggested for these two types of currents.

In the case of Brdicka currents, at less than 20% of saturation value (maximum current) the currents are kinetic in nature and at saturation value the current depends on metal ion concentration due to transport by diffusion of the metal complex to the mercury surface. A two-electron reduction of cobalt(II)-thiolate complex occurs at the electrode to form zerovalent cobalt-thiolate complex. This complex remains at the electrode and due to its increased basicity it reacts with protons (rate-determining step) which on further reduction liberates hydrogen,

$[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{RS})_x(\text{D})_y(\text{H}_2\text{O})_z]_0$ at the electrode also must have been obtained by the following scheme from the thiol-free species reaching the electrode surface which will follow the routes (2)-(4) mentioned above,

↓
complexation

where D refers to basic buffer constituent and subscript, zero, refers to the surface of the electrode.

In the second type the maximum 'A' is considered to be due to direct protonation of the cobalt(II)-thiolate complex at the surface of the electrode and the protonated complex getting reduced to generate molecular hydrogen. The wave has an adsorption kinetic character.

The origin of maximum 'B' in the second type of non-Brdicka current is stated to be from the decomposition of the cobalt(0)-thiolate complex into thiol and cobalt(0) metal. The freshly deposited metallic cobalt liberates molecular hydrogen and thiolate ion, RS⁻ becomes RSH. The wave is surface-kinetic in character.

The direct discharge of hydronium ion on the stabilized atom of metallic cobalt on the surface of the mercury may also be from the thiol-free species existing in solution before complexation,

Of these two mechanisms suggested for maximum 'B', the first one due to decomposition of complex to give Co(0) metal seems to be more reasonable and requires further attention.

In this field of catalytic hydrogen waves with thio compounds, we studied a few thio compound complexes of chromium(vi,iii), iron(ii), cobalt(ii) and nickel(ii) in ammonium chloride-ammonia buffer and developed sensitive and selective methods for their estimation in natural samples.

The catalytic hydrogen waves of Cr^{VI} were first identified in these laboratories at -1.2 to -1.6 V vs SCE at DME as a single peak with thio compounds, such as pentamethylene dithiocarbamate, diethyl dithiocarbamate, ammonium pyrrolidine dithiocarbamate, potassium ethyl xanthate, potassium butyl xanthate (KbXan), sodium isopropyl xanthate (Napxan) and potassium benzyl xanthate (Kbenxan) as complexing agents⁶⁵⁻⁷². The peak current was found to be useful for the determination of chromium at nanogram level. The method was applied to determine trace amounts of chromium in drinking water, industrial effluents, tannery waste water, unpolished rice, betel leaves, *Oscimum sanctum* leaves, ores and stainless steel samples. Zou Yongming *et al.*⁷³ later developed sensitive second derivative technique for the catalytic wave of chromium(vi)-aminoquinoline-azophenyl sulfonate complex for nanogram quantities of the metal ion.

Iron(ii) gave catalytic hydrogen waves at DME at about -1.0 to -1.4 V vs SCE in the presence of xanthates (Kbenxan, Kbxan, Napxan) as complexing agents. The current was proportional to the Fe^{II} concentration in the range 0.1-2.8 ppm and water, leafy vegetables and pharmaceuticals were analysed for the metal ion using this method^{74,77}.

The catalytic hydrogen waves at DME due to cobalt(ii) in the potential range of -0.8 to -1.2 V vs SCE with Kbenxan, Kbxan and Napxan in aqueous media were used to determine trace amounts of cobalt in water samples and agricultural samples^{75,79}. The polarographic behaviour of nickel(ii) at mercury in ammonium chloride-ammonium hydroxide buffer in the presence of xanthates was studied and a catalytic hydrogen wave at about -0.8 to -1.2 V vs SCE was found to be useful for analysis of nickel content in water samples and agricultural materials^{76,79}.

Cyclic voltammograms of Fe^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II}-xanthate (Kbenxan, Kbxan and Napxan) complexes were recorded at an HMDE at different sweep rates from 0.04 to 0.32 V⁻¹ in order to supplement the results of d.c. polarography. A cathodic peak was observed corresponding to the catalytic maximum of d.c. polarography and no anodic peak was found at the corresponding anodic potentials. The catalytic wave nature was evidenced from current function $i_p v^{-1/2}$. The kinetic character of the catalytic current was indicated by the current increase with scan rate v , and decrease of the current function $i_p v^{-1/2}$ with increasing scan rate, and also from the plot $v^{-1/2}$ vs $i_p v^{-1/2}$. These results indicate that the cathodic peak current are due to catalytic hydrogen waves and are of Brdicka type and confirmed the involvement of metal-xanthate complexes in the form of M(0)RS⁷⁸. Some more experimental results are required to indicate the species responsible for catalytic hydrogen currents to establish the mechanism fully as suggested earlier¹⁴.

In conclusion, it can be stated that polarographic catalytic hydrogen waves caused by the presence of organic ligands containing -SH groups provide one of the most sensitive analytical methods for the determination of trace and ultra-trace quantities of many transition metal ions in ores, alloys, environmental, biological, agricultural and pharmaceutical samples.

References

1. L. MEITES, "Polarographic Techniques", Interscience, New York, 1965.
2. S.G. MAIRANOVSKII, "Catalytic and Kinetic Waves in Polarography", Plenum, New York, 1968.
3. S. G. MAIRANOVSKII, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1963, **6**, 77.
4. J. KORYTA, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1967, **15**, 207.
5. J. BOGNAR, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1971, **75**, 70709.
6. S.I. SINYAKOVA, V.F. TOROPOVA, and L.A. MILYAVSKII, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1973, **78**, 168049.
7. N. CHIZUKO and M. HIROAKI, *J. Electroanal. Chem. Interfacial Electrochem.*, 1974, **51**, 287.
8. K. SHEAU-SHYA, *Hua Hsueh Tung Pao*, 1979, **4**, 297 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1979, **91**, 148273).
9. K. SHEAU-SHYA, *Hua Hsueh Hsueh Pao*, 1980, **1**, 121 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1981, **94**, 149497).
10. K. SHEAU-SHYA, *Rev. Anal. Chem.*, 1983, **7**, 56.
11. N. A. EZERSKAYA and I. N. KISELEVA, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1984, **39**, 1541.
12. L. YA. KHEIFETS and P. M. ZAITSEV, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1989, **44**, 986.
13. I. M. KOLTHOFF and P. MADER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1970, **42**, 1762.
14. P. MADER, I. M. KOLTHOFF, and V. VESELA, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1982, **22**, 1393.

15. R. GOLDSTEIN and M. KONIGSBUCH, *Isr. J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 65.
16. B. A. KUZNETSOV, *Experientia*, Suppl. 1971, **18**, 381 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1972, **77**, 123535).
17. M. SENDA, T. IKEDA, T. KAKUTANI, K. KANO, and H. KINOSHITA, *Bioelectrochem. Bioenerg.*, 1981, **8**, 151.
18. M. SENDA, T. IKEDA, K. KANO, and I. TOKIMITSU, *Bioelectrochem. Bioenerg.*, 1982, **9**, 253.
19. K. KANO, I. TOKIMITSU, T. IKEDA, and M. SENDA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1984, **57**, 648.
20. J. M. LOPEZ-FONSECA, *An. Real. Acad. Farm.*, 1971, **37**, 385 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1971, **75**, 1080).
21. P. ANZERBACHER and V. KALOUS, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1972, **37**, 3209 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1973, **78**, 10857).
22. N. VANLAETHIEM-MEUREE, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1975, **20**, 45.
23. G. N. BABKIN, L. N. LEBEDEVA, and V. P. GLADYSHEV, *Dokl. Vses. Soveshch. Polyarogr.*, 1975, **6**, 178 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, **85**, 200068).
24. J. KADLECEK, P. ANZENBACHER, and V. KALOUS, *J. Electroanal. Chem. Interfacial Electrochem.*, 1978, **86**, 417.
25. B. JOHANSSON and S. WENDSJO, *J. Electroanal. Chem. Interfacial Electrochem.*, 1984, **167**, 165.
26. I. M. KOLTHOFF, K. YAMASHITA, and H. TAN BOEN., *J. Electroanal. Chem. Interfacial Electrochem.*, 1975, **63**, 393.
27. H. KINOSHITA, T. IKEDA, Y. YAMUNE, and M. SENDA, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1980, **44**, 2337.
28. M. KUIK, K. KRASSOWSKI, and A. CZERNIAK, *Bioelectrochem. Bioenerg.*, 1981, **8**, 141.
29. M. KUIK and K. KRASSOWSKI, *Bioelectrochem. Bioenerg.*, 1982, **9**, 419.
30. R. S. SAXENA and U. S. CHATURVEDI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 1402.
31. J. KADLECEK, P. ANZENBACHER, and V. KALOUS, *J. Electroanal. Chem. Interfacial Electrochem.*, 1975, **61**, 141.
32. J. KADLECEK and V. KALOUS, *J. Electroanal. Chem. Interfacial Electrochem.*, 1979, **105**, 225.
33. J. M. L. FONSECA, C. G. POSA, and P. S. PEDRERO, *An. Quim., Ser. A*, 1981, **77**, 357 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1982, **97**, 30204).
34. J. GALVEZ, D. MARIN, J. FUENTE, and M. SARABIA, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1984, **29**, 253.
35. T. P. RUIZ and J. M. M. MORENO, *Quim. Anal.*, 1984, **3**, 180 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1985, **103**, 31797).
36. Z. ZHAO and Y. WANG, *Huaxue Xuebao*, 1983, **41**, 761 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1983, **99**, 205190).
37. Z. GAO, K. S. SLOW, and L. YEO, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1996, **320**, 229.
38. G. K. BUDNIKOV, V. F. TOROPOVA, N. A. ULAKHOVICH, E. P. MEDYANTSEVA, and V. P. FROLOVA, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1977, **32**, 212.
39. V. F. TOROPOVA, G. K. BUDNIKOV, and E. P. MEDYANTSEVA, *Zh. Obshch. Khim.*, 1975, **45**, 1366 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1975, **83**, 138956).
40. G. K. BUDNIKOV, V. F. TOROPOVA, N. A. ULAKHOVICH, and I. P. VITER, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1974, **29**, 752 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1975, **82**, 12067).
41. G. K. BUDNIKOV, N. A. ULAKHOVICH, E. P. MEDYANTSEVA, I. P. VITER, and V. F. TOROPOVA, *Zh. Obshch. Khim.*, 1976, **46**, 2094 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, **85**, 200073).
42. V. F. TOROPOVA, G. K. BUDNIKOV, V. P. FROLOVA, and N. A. ULAKHOVICH, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1977, **32**, 1850 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, **88**, 163261).
43. V. P. FROLOVA, N. A. ULAKHOVICH, and G. K. BUDNIKOV, Deposited Doc. SP STL 12 Khp-D80, 1980, 9.
44. M. KUIK, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1971, **36**, 1009 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1971, **74**, 119410).
45. M. KUIK, *Rocz. Chem.*, 1971, **45**, 285 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1971, **75**, 14235).
46. F. G. BANICA and A. CALUSARU, *J. Electroanal. Chem. Interfacial Electrochem.*, 1983, **145**, 389.
47. F. G. BANICA and A. CALUSARU, *J. Electroanal. Chem. Interfacial Electrochem.*, 1983, **158**, 47.
48. C. AURELIAN, M. MARIA, and O. MINAELA, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1994, **39**, 1025 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1995, **123**, 95992).
49. E. BANICA, F. GALOREEL, and I. ION, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1994, **39**, 283 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1995, **122**, 91347).
50. Z. ZHENGQI, Z. S. ZONG, C. ZHAOPENG, and L. XIAOLI, *Fenxi Shiyanshi*, 1992, **11**, 21 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1993, **119**, 61831).
51. J. BIERNAT and A. SYZMASZEK, *Bull. Acad. Pol. Sci., Ser. Sci. Chem.*, 1976, **24**, 133 (*Chem. Abstr.* 1976, **85**, 11618).
52. R. PALANIAPPAN and V. REVATHI, *J. Indian Counc. Chem.*, 1988, **4**, 1.
53. Z. HUANG and X. DU, *Huanjing Huaxue*, 1988, **7**, 72 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1988, **109**, 236563).
54. A. M. PERCIO, FARIAS, L. C. S. FERREIRA, A. K. OHARA, M. B. BASTOS, and M. S. GOULART, *Talanta*, 1992, **39**, 1245.
55. X. DU, R. FENG, and Z. HUANG, *Fenxi Huaxue*, 1987, **15**, 240 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1987, **107**, 161188).
56. X. DU and Z. HUANG, *Fenxi Huaxue*, 1989, **17**, 276 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1989, **111**, 63638).
57. E. P. MEDYANTSEVA, G. K. BUDNIKOV, O. N. ROMANOVA, and I. V. ZHIVOLOP, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1987, **42**, 1846 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1988, **108**, 105442).
58. I. N. KISELEVA, N. A. EZERSKAYA, and T. P. SOLOVYKH, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1973, **18**, 778 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1973, **79**, 38112).
59. N. A. EZERSKAYA, Y. V. GRANOVSKII, I. N. KISELEVA, L. K. SUBOCHKIN, and O. S. SHEUCHENKO, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1977, **32**, 2201.
60. N. A. EZERSKAYA, I. N. KISELEVA, I. L. KAZAKEVICH, N. V. GERBELEU, and L. K. SUBOCHKIN, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1984, **39**, 654.
61. Y. ZHOU, A. ZHANG, and J. ZHANG, *Fenxi Huaxue*, 1985, **13**, 556 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1985, **104**, 198974).
62. Z. ZHENYI, Z. GUANG, and F. Y. YUAN., *Huaxue Xuebao*, 1992, **50**, 1117 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1993, **118**, 115836).
63. G. M. RAFI and A. PAUL, *Curr. Sci.*, 1982, **51**, 350.
64. DEZHONG DAN and JUNE RE, *Talanta*, 1992, **39**, 119.
65. K. SARASWATHI, K. SANTHA, and K. MEENAKUMARI, *Analyst*, 1990, **115**, 465.
66. K. SARASWATHI, K. YAMUNA, and K. A. EMMANUEL, *J. Electrochem. Soc. India*, 1990, **39**, 122.
67. K. SARASWATHI, K. A. EMMANUEL, and K. YAMUNA, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 1990, **6**, 953.
68. K. SARASWATHI, K. YAMUNA and K. A. EMMANUEL, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1991, **103**, 185.
69. K. SARASWATHI and K. YAMUNA, *J. Electrochem. Soc. India*, 1992, **41**, 135.
70. K. SARASWATHI, '14th International Symposium on Analytical Chemistry', Ontario, 1990.
71. K. SARASWATHI and K. YAMUNA, UGC Seminar on 'Assessment of Impact of Industries, Nuclear and Thermal Power Plants and Oil Exploration Activities on Environment', Visakhapatnam, 1991.
72. K. SARASWATHI and K. YAMUNA, 'National Seminar on Electrochemical Studies', Anantapur, "Seminar Handbook", 1991, p.10.
73. Z. YONGMING, D. Z. TAO, and W. B. L. SONGYU, *Fenxi Huaxue*, 1994, **22**, 1115 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1995, **123**, 73589).

74. K. SARASWATHI and K. YAMUNA, '10th Annual Conference of Indian Council of Chemists', Goa, 1991, Abstract No. A0-63.
75. K. SARASWATHI and K. YAMUNA, '28th Annual Convention of Chemists', Calcutta, 1991, Abstract No. ANAL-5.7.
76. K. SARASWATHI and K. YAMUNA, 'Workshop on Interaction of 'Research Activities in Industries and Academic Institutes in India-Recent Trends in Analytical Chemistry Teaching and Research in Indian Universities', Mumbai, "Seminar Handbook", 1992, p. 151.
77. K. YAMUNA and K. SARASWATHI, 'PITTCO'93' Atlanta, 1993, Ab. No. 1320.
78. K. YAMUNA, Ph.D. Thesis, S.V. University, 1994.
79. K. YAMUNA, 'PITTCO'95', New Orleans, 1995, Ab. No. 1167.